

METHODOLOGY FOR DEVELOPING THE ORAL SPEECH OF HEARING-IMPAIRED CHILDREN WITH COCHLEAR IMPLANTS IN NATIVE LANGUAGE CLASSES WITHIN THE GENERAL EDUCATION PROCESS

Isoqjonova Dilfuzaxon

Teacher of the Department of “Surdopedagogy and Clinical Foundations of Special Pedagogy” Uzbekistan National Pedagogical University

Abstract. Speech is an important means in human social life. In the process of integration into society, speech emerges as a primary tool of interpersonal communication. Speech disorders that arise as a secondary problem in children with hearing impairments negatively affect their overall development and socialization. This article discusses the content of work aimed at developing speech communication skills in children with hearing impairments who have undergone cochlear implantation surgery, as well as the organization of speech rehabilitation.

Keywords: student with a cochlear implant, speech acquisition, vocabulary development, communicative skills, collaborative interaction, adaptation of education.

Introduction. According to R.M. Boskis, one of the key criteria determining the role of hearing in children’s overall development is the independence in acquiring speech. In children with normal hearing, this process occurs naturally, whereas in children with hearing impairments it is achieved through special instruction, since they cannot independently use their residual hearing to acquire speech and expand their vocabulary [1]. Therefore, work on speech holds a special significance in surdopedagogy. The development of modern science and technology has made it possible today to use cochlear implant devices to address hearing problems. After implantation, organizing auditory-speech rehabilitation for children with hearing impairments serves as a foundation for ensuring their overall development, socialization, and full integration into the general education system. Taking this into account, there arises a need to create various new directions and methodologies for speech rehabilitation.

Literature Review on the Topic. The problem of developing the oral speech of individuals with hearing impairments has long been considered one of the most pressing issues in surdopedagogy. Throughout the stages of development of surdopedagogy, many scholars, including F.F. Rau, R.M. Boskis, E.P. Kuzmicheva, L.V. Neyman, I.G. Bagrova, L.P. Nazarova, N.D. Shmatko, T.V. Pelymskaya, L.A. Golovchits, and L.P. Noskova devoted their work to solving speech-related problems. In recent years, the practical significance of cochlear implantation in the rehabilitation of hearing impairments and the issues of speech rehabilitation of children with cochlear implants have been studied by Russian scholars such as I.V. Koroleva, O.V. Zontova, G.A. Tavartkiladze, E.I. Mironova, N.V. Tarasova, A.A.

Balyakova, A.I. Sataeva, and M. Leongard. Among Uzbek scholars, Z.N. Mamarajabova, D.A. Nazarova, U.Yu. Fayziyeva, R. Rustamova, X.S. Rakhimova, D.U. Mukhitdinova, and N.Z. Rakhmonova have investigated in their works the development of oral speech in children with hearing impairments and the problems of rehabilitation of children with cochlear implants.

Communicative skills form the foundation of a child's speech activity. These include elements such as hearing, speaking, understanding, exchanging ideas, listening comprehension, and perceiving voice intonation. Developing such skills in children with cochlear implants requires a specific approach, since even after implantation a child may not always naturally perceive the hearing process; in some cases, the differentiation of sounds or their correct interpretation may be impaired. Therefore, from the very early stages of speech rehabilitation, it is necessary to apply an individual approach, systematic training sessions, and to introduce special speech-therapy and pedagogical techniques [2]. According to I. Korolyova, when a child undergoes implantation after the age of two, the spontaneous development of speech comprehension and the acquisition of expressive speech begins later—approximately 8–12 months afterward. This process directly depends on several factors: the degree of residual hearing development at the time of implantation, the level of formation of pronunciation skills, the age at implantation, parental involvement in the child's development, and the presence of additional impairments, among others [3]. The above considerations indicate that the earlier and more systematically oral speech development is organized in children with cochlear implants, the higher the effectiveness of the outcomes. The age at implantation also plays a significant role in the child's adaptation to school education and full integration into inclusive settings. Once a child enters school, the need for oral speech in mastering academic subjects increases even further; however, in some cases, the child's speech abilities may not be sufficient to meet this need. Therefore, each lesson process requires an individualized approach to the child.

Research Methodology. In this scientific study, the conditions for developing the oral speech of hearing-impaired children with cochlear implants in native language lessons were analyzed. The research was based on the theories proposed by surdopedagogical scholars, the possibilities of modern special education, and the fundamental principles of educating students with hearing impairments.

Analysis and Results. It is advisable that the system of activities organized during the lesson be based on auditory, visual, and kinesthetic perceptions. The methodological system for organizing the lesson process should be structured in a последователь (sequential) manner through individual and group tasks. This system of exercises should appropriately include the following directions:

- Phonetic-hearing exercises;
- Lexical exercises;
- Exercises aimed at developing sentence formation and connected speech;
- Exercises for developing dialogic and monologic speech;

- Multisensory exercises.

For lesson effectiveness and successful learning, mutual cooperation between the teacher and the student is required. In particular, working with a student who has a cochlear implant in the educational process requires the following practical methods:

❖ The teacher should provide the lesson topic to the child in advance. This allows time to analyze new terms and vocabulary related to the topic together, helping the child learn to recognize them by hearing, and makes it easier for the child to grasp the lesson during class;

❖ First, the student's attention should be directed to the teacher's face. Speech should be delivered with normal, natural articulation, proper speech rate, and intonation;

❖ It is necessary to ask the student using the cochlear implant to repeat instructions, so the teacher can ensure that the student has correctly understood the task;

❖ Sentences addressed to the student should begin with familiar words that are easily perceived by hearing or with words whose meaning has been previously explained to the child;

❖ If the child does not understand the sentence the first time, it should be repeated without changing the word order;

❖ It is necessary to develop speech behavior in the child, that is, to teach them to pay attention to the speech of others (peers, adults);

❖ For students using a cochlear implant, perceiving speech becomes more difficult in noisy environments and over long distances. These factors should be taken into account when arranging the classroom, meaning the child should be seated close to the teacher;

❖ The general education school curriculum involves studying many subjects. Each subject contains specialized vocabulary and terminology, which may be difficult for students with cochlear implants to perceive. Therefore, great attention should be given to vocabulary work, clarifying word meanings, and developing an academic-terminological lexicon [4].

In addition, the following are recommended as supplementary aids:

- New words and terms should be written on cards and placed on the student's desk before the start of the lesson;
- Use various types of visual materials;
- Use of context;
- Use the problem-based method for semantic development of vocabulary.

Teachers in general education schools face difficulties when teaching children with cochlear implants, as they often lack sufficient competence in providing specialized support. Therefore, the following recommendations can assist teachers in educating children with cochlear implants:

✓ To help the child better grasp the topic, the "pre-teaching" method can be recommended. That is, the child studies the topic independently or with their parents at home, and during the lesson, the student with a cochlear implant reinforces it.

✓ It is important that no learning material remains misunderstood, as this may lead to difficulties in mastering subsequent sections.

✓ Studying the curriculum material in the native language may present particular difficulties. In addition to traditional tasks, the teacher can also assign corrective exercises; for example, working on correcting the grammatical structure of speech characteristic of students with hearing impairments.

✓ The teacher can modify tasks taking into account the abilities of the student using a cochlear implant. For example, instead of a complex task planned in the exercise, the teacher may present a relatively simpler task.

✓ The teacher should aim to ensure that within the scope of the topic, through individual tasks, the student using a cochlear implant practices forming word combinations, sentences, and short texts.

✓ The teacher should be aware of the mistakes the student makes while completing tasks and consistently provide appropriate exercises to reinforce their knowledge on the topic. Textbooks can be used in this process, and such exercises are recommended for the student with a cochlear implant as practice. Special attention should be given to clarifying the sound-letter composition of words.

✓ When administering written dictations, it is necessary to take into account the hearing and speech abilities of the student using a cochlear implant. If the child's hearing and speech skills are sufficient, they can write the dictation along with the rest of the class. However, it is recommended to provide additional preparation before the dictation, which involves introducing the child in advance to the topic of the dictation. This allows the student to navigate the content of the dictation more easily. The student should also be familiarized beforehand with the most difficult words and word combinations in terms of sound-letter composition, meaning, and grammatical structure.

Key observations indicate that within 1–2 years after implantation, children almost catch up with their normally hearing peers. The level of speech comprehension develops more rapidly with regular practice. Children receiving education with the help of a cochlear implant achieve positive socialization in inclusive classrooms. When speech therapists, surdopedagogues, and parents work together, the child's psychological adaptation becomes significantly easier [5]. Moreover, over time during the educational process, students gradually develop greater self-confidence, improved communication skills, and better adaptation to the learning process and environment [6]. A child's adaptation to the educational process and the improvement of speech and hearing efficiency directly depend on a continuous and properly organized pedagogical approach. Ensuring continuity in the pedagogical process relies not only on the methods used during lessons but also on the social-pedagogical support provided by parents and close family members at home. Additionally, to ensure effective learning, the teaching staff of the general education school must understand the developmental characteristics of the child with a cochlear implant, study the specific features of their cognitive abilities, and select appropriate directions and strategies tailored to the child.

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